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On the checklist of Ukrainian Diptera Tephritoidea: Ulidiidae, Platystomatidae, Pyrgotidae

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Kameneva, E. P., Popov, G. V. & Korneyev, V. A. On the checklist of Ukrainian Diptera Tephritoidea: Ulidiidae, Platystomatidae, Pyrgotidae. — The species from three families of the higher tephritoid flies hitherto recorded from Ukraine are listed with references. Of them, *Ulidia parallela* is recorded from Ukraine for the first time, and 3 species (*Melieria picta*, *Physiphora alceae* and *Platystoma frauenfeldi*) are recorded for the first time from Kharkiv, Ternopil and Khmelnytsky Regions, correspondingly. Thirty-seven species of picture-winged flies (Ulidiidae), six species of signal flies (Platystomatidae) and one species of pyrgotid flies (Pyrgotidae) are known to occur in Ukraine.

Key words: Diptera, Tephritoidea, Ulidiidae, Platystomatidae, Pyrgotidae, Ukraine, flies, checklist.

Каменєва, О. П., Попов, Г. В. і Корнеєв, В. О. До чек-листу українських видів двокрилих підродини Tephritoidea: Ulidiidae, Platystomatidae, Pyrgotidae. — Анотований перелік видів з трьох родин вищих тефритоїдних мух, досі були зареєстрованих в Україні. З них уперше в Україні знайдено *Ulidia parallela*, а 3 види — *Melieria picta*, *Physiphora alceae* та *Platystoma frauenfeldi* — вперше зазначено з Харківської, Тернопільської та Хмельницької областей, відповідно. Усього в Україні зустрічаються тридцять сім видів мухи-стрічкокрилок (Ulidiidae), шість видів мух-сигнальниць (Platystomatidae) та один вид мух-пірготид (Pyrgotidae).

Ключові слова: Diptera, Tephritoidea, Ulidiidae, Platystomatidae, Pyrgotidae, Ukraine, мухи, список видів.

Introduction

In the dipteran superfamily Tephritoidea, the families Platystomatidae, Ulidiidae, and Pyrgotidae, with approximately 1200, 200 and 350 valid species names follow the Tephritidae with the *ca.* 4900 species (Norrbon, pers. comm.; Pape *et al.*, 2011 with addenda: Korneyev, unpublished data). Most Ulidiidae and Platystomatidae species of known biology are saprophagous and live under the bark of fallen trees (Korneyev, 1999), in stems of grasses and palms infested by beetle larvae or caterpillars (Korneyev, Volovnik & Popov, 2015; Kameneva & Korneyev, 2016); under the ground in the onions of liliopsid plants and nitrogen nodules of leguminose grasses and trees or in decomposing plant and animal tissues (Ferrar, 1987); larvae of some New World ulidiids also live inside bamboo stems, feeding as saprophages (Kovac, Kameneva, Korneyev *et al.*, in preparation).

Studies of the tephritoid flies in Ukraine began with the description of *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld,

1867 (Tephritidae) and a list of flies collected in Podolien (now Ternopil Region of Ukraine) in 1866 by Antony Wierzejski, a naturalist and student of Prof. Maximillian Sila Nowicki from the University of Krakow; these flies were identified by M. Novicki, G.R. von Frauenfeld and I. R. Schiner; collection is mostly available at the State Museum of Natural History, Lviv (SMNHL) and partly at the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NHMW). Later, Jaroszewski (1877, 1880, 1884) has published a series of Diptera lists based on his collection specimens identified mostly by I.A. Portsinsky and deposited now mainly at the Zoological Institute, Saint Peterburg (ZISP). A few species of Tephritoidea were collected in 1933–1936 in the Middle Dnipro Area, identified by A. A. Stackelberg and then published by O. P. Kryshthal (1949). In the last 40 years, a vast material was collected by V. A. Korneyev & E. P. Kameneva in different parts of Ukraine and then partly published (see the checklist below).

No comprehensive catalogues of Palaearctic species were published since Soós (1984 a, 1984 b, 1984 c) and Zaitzev (1984). The only lists or databases of European species are those of Greve & Kameneva (2013), Korneyev (2013) and Merz (2013). Priority of the family name Ulidiidae Macquart, 1835 over Otitidae Aldrich, 1931 was demonstrated by Kameneva & Korneyev (1994) and is universally accepted since then.

Currently, the number of Ulidiidae, Platystomatidae and Pyrgotidae species is close to the estimated. We expect at most 2–3 additional species of the Ulidiidae (*Otites*, *Homalocephala*, *Herina*) in the Carpathian mountains and steppes and 1–2 additional species of Platystomatidae in Crimea and south-eastern part of Ukraine.

The territory of Ukraine is unevenly covered by collecting, and many field and museum specimens are to be added to the Ukrainian National Biodiversity Information Network (UkrBIN, 2020b). This certainly would expand the known distribution of most species in the country now restricted to a few popular localities in the neighbourhood of big cities.

The current paper provides a list of species based on the published data with a few previously unpublished additions.

Genera and species are given in alphabetical order within each family.

In **Distribution**, the provinces (Regions, Oblasts), are listed from the West to East and from the North to South.

As the result, thirty-seven species of Ulidiidae, six species of Platystomatidae and one species of Pyrgotidae are listed. Of them, *Ulidia parallela* Loew, 1845 is recorded from Ukraine for the first time, and 3 species (*Meliera picta*, *Physiphora alceae* and *Platystoma frauenfeldi*) are recorded for the first time from Kharkiv, Ternopil and Khmelnytsky Regions, correspondingly.

List of species

Ulidiidae

Callopiostromyia annulipes (Macquart, 1855)

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

References. Korneyev, Kameneva & Korneyev, 2018; Dvořák et al., 2019.

Remarks. Invasive Nearctic species; saprophagous; often in garbage; attracted to beer traps.

Cephalia rufipes Meigen, 1826

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

References. Wierzejski, 1867.

Remarks. No specimens examined.

Ceroxys cinifera (Loew, 1846)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson.

References. Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

Ceroxys hortulana (Rossi, 1790)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Kirovohrad; Poltava; Kharkiv; Zaporizhzhia; Odesa; Mykolaiv.

References. Jaroszewski, 1880 (as “*Ceroxys hyalinata* Panzer”); Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

Ceroxys munda (Loew, 1868)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Vinnytsia, Cherkasy, Zaporizhzhia, Luhansk, Odesa, Kherson.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

Ceroxys urticae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Ternopil, Donetsk, Odesa, Kherson.

References. Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 2 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL); Kyiv: Irpin, 50.5278°N, 30.2650°E, 18.05.1996, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

Dorycera hybrida Loew, 1862

Distribution in Ukraine: Odesa.

References. Kameneva, 2000.

Euxesta notata (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

References. Korneyev, Kameneva & Korneyev, 2018; Dvořák et al., 2019.

Remarks. Invasive Nearctic species; saprophagous; often in garbage; attracted to beer traps.

Euxesta pechumani Curran, 1938

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska, Zaporizhzhia.

References. Kameneva, 1992; 2008; Korneyev, Kameneva & Korneyev, 2018; Dvořák et al., 2019.

Remarks. Invasive Nearctic species; saprophagous; often on dead tree trunks; attracted to beer traps.

Herina aartseni Merz, 2002

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea.

References. Kameneva, 2000 (as *H. lugubris*; misidentificaiton); 2008.

Herina frondescentiae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn, Zhytomyr, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Ternopil.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 4 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Herina paludum* (Fallén, 1820)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

References. Wierzejski, 1867.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 1 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Herina palustris* (Meigen, 1826)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Ternopil.

References. Wierzejski, 1867; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2007.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 1 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Homalocephala angustata* (Wahlberg, 1839)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Additional material. Ternopil: (?) Skala Podolska, 3.05.1866, 1 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

Remarks. Doubtful identification. Head missing.

***Homalocephala biumbrata* (Wahlberg, 1839)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.

References. Kameneva, 2002a, 2008.

Remarks. On poplar logs.

***Melieria (Melieria) acuticornis* (Loew, 1854)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Poltava, Kherson.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

***Melieria (Melieria) cana* (Loew, 1858)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson, Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

***Melieria (Melieria) crassipennis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn, Zhytomyr, Kyiv, Ternopil, Cherkasy, Poltava, Dnipropetrovsk.

References. Kryshstal, 1949; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2008.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 10 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Melieria (Melieria) nigritarsis* Becker, 1903**

Distribution in Ukraine: Zaporizhzhia, Donetsk.

References. Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

***Melieria (Melieria) omissa* (Meigen, 1826)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Kherson.

References. Jaroszewski, 1877; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000.

***Melieria (Melieria) picta* (Meigen, 1826)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Cherkasy, Kharkiv (**first record**), Mykolaiv, Kherson, Crimea.

References. Kryshstal, 1949; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000, 2008.

Remarks. Additional material: Kharkiv: Zmiiv Distr., Haydary, 49.6280°N, 36.3345°E, sweeping from shore vegetation, 23.06.2009, 4 ♂ (Guglya) (SIZK).

***Myennis octopunctata* (Coquebert, 1798)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Kharkiv, Donetsk, Kherson, Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski, 1878 (as “*Myennis fasciata*”); Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2008; Dvořák et al., 2019; UkrBIN, 2020a.

Remarks. On dead or wounded poplars; larvae under the dead bark.

***Myennis sibirica* Portschinsky, 1892**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.

References. Kameneva, Korneyev & Prokhorov, 2013.

Remarks. Apparently invasive, Far East Asian species. On bleeding oaks.

***Otites centralis* (Fabricius, 1805)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Ternopil, Cherkasy, Kirovohrad, Kharkiv, Luhansk, Odesa.

References. Jaroszewski, 1878; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 1 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

Remarks. Usual in oak woods, adults underneath oak leaves.

***Otites guttata* (Meigen, 1830)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

References. Kameneva, 2000.

***Otites lamed* (Schrank, 1781)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy, Donetsk, Odesa, Mykolaiv, Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski, 1887; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000.

***Otites nebulosa* (Latreille, 1811)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Kirovohrad.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2000.

***Otites ruficeps* (Fabricius, 1805)**

Normenclature. Kameneva & Korneyev, 2019: 26.

Musca formosa Panzer, [1798] (preoccupied name, non *Musca formosa* Scopoli, 1763); *Otites formosa*: Hennig, 1939; Soós, 1984 c; Kameneva, 1997, 2000; Greve & Kameneva, 2013; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987.

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy, Kirovohrad, Poltava, Dnipropetrovsk, Luhansk, Odesa, Kherson, Mykolaiv, Zaporizhzhia, Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 1997 (as *Otites formosa*).

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 6 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Physiphora alceae* (Preyssl, 1791)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil (first record); Cherkasy, Odesa, Kherson, Zaporizhzhia, Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987 (as *P. demandata*), 2016.

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 8spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Pseudoseioptera demonstrans* (Hennig, 1941)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.

References. Kameneva, 2002b, 2008.

Remarks. On poplar logs; rarely.

***Seioptera vibrans* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Zhytomyr, Vinnytsia, Cherkasy, Dnipropetrovsk, Luhansk, Odesa, Mykolaiv, Zaporizhzhia, Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2008.

***Tetanops (Eurycephalomyia) sintenisi* Becker, 1909**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2008.

***Tetanops (Tetanops) myopina* Fallén, 1820**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Cherkasy.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Kameneva, 2008.

Remarks. In sandy dunes.

***Timia (Empyelocera) abstersa* (Loew, 1873)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Zaporizhzhia, Odesa, Mykolaiv, Kherson.

References. Kameneva, 2008.

***Ulidia erythrophthalma* Meigen, 1826**

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska, Cherkasy, Kirovohrad, Dnipropetrovsk, Odesa, Mykolaiv, Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987.

***Ulidia nigripennis* Loew, 1845**

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Ternopil, Kharkiv.

References. Jaroszewski, 1884; Kameneva, 2008.

Additional material. Ternopil: Pantalycha, 49.31°N, 25.45°E, 29.07.1866, 1 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

***Ulidia parallela* Loew, 1845**

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil (first record from Ukraine).

References. Kameneva, 2008 (redescription, distribution).

Additional material. Ternopil: Synkiv, 48.63°N, 25.94°E, 25.06.1866, 2 spm. (A. Wierzejski) (SMNHL).

Platystomatidae***Platystoma frauenfeldi* Nowicki, 1867**

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Khmelnytsky (first record).

References. Nowicki, 1867.

Remarks. Additional material: Khmelnytsky: 2 km W of Dunayivtsi, 15.07.1989, 1 ♂ (Zrazhevsky) (SIZK).

***Platystoma lugubre* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987.

***Platystoma rufipes* Meigen, 1826**

Distribution in Ukraine: Donetsk, Zaporizhzhia, Crimea.

References. Korneyev & Volovnik & Popov, 2015.

Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Crambe* (Brassicaceae) feeding in pupation chamber together with dead pupa of the weevil *Lixus (Eulixus) canescens* Steven.

***Platystoma seminationis* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Distribution in Ukraine: Lviv, Kirovohrad, Kharkiv, Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski, 1878; Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987; Zimina, 1993.

Remarks. Additional material: Lviv: Olesko, 49.9695°N, 24.8964°E, 3.06.2010, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

Rivellia syngenesiae (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev, 1987.

Remarks. Widespread throughout Ukraine; larvae in the root nodules on various leguminose grasses (Seegar & Maldagne, 1960; Ferrar, 1987; Foote et al., 1987).

Pyrgotidae

Adapsilia coarctata Waga, 1842

Distribution in Ukraine: Kharkiv.

References. Jaroszewski, 1884.

Remarks. A very rare species in Europe, occasionally recorded from a few European countries (Nartshuk, 2004; Korneyev, 2009). In Ukraine was recorded only once, from Chuhuyiv in the end of July, 1983. The specimen apparently lost.

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